

Tropical plants to reduce chronic metabolic diseases in the obesity pandemic: a narrative review

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Academic Editor: Bahram Arjmandi

Abstract

Introduction: Chronic metabolic diseases such as diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular disease are a major challenge to global health. Functional foods from tropical plants, especially those rich in bioactive compounds like flavonoids and polyphenols, have shown potential in reducing the risk of these diseases. **Objective:** This study aims to review the scientific evidence on ten tropical plants selected for their high polyphenol content and potential effectiveness in reducing the risk of metabolic diseases, focusing on their bioactive compositions and metabolic health impacts. **Materials and Methods:** A comprehensive literature review was conducted using PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus to identify studies examining the phytochemical properties of tropical plants and their link to modulating metabolic risk factors for chronic metabolic disease. **Results:** The findings suggest that the selected plants' bioactive compounds, such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and carotenoids, may benefit metabolic health through mechanisms like reducing oxidative stress, modulating inflammation, and regulating lipid and glucose metabolism. **Conclusions:** Functional foods derived from tropical plants present a promising approach to reducing the risk of chronic metabolic diseases. Nonetheless, further studies are necessary to clarify their mechanisms and confirm effectiveness in larger clinical trials. This review underscores the rich biodiversity of tropical plants as a significant source of therapeutic bioactive compounds.

Keywords: *functional foods, bioactive compounds, chronic metabolic diseases, tropical plants, disease prevention, South America*

Citation: Ayala Franco M, Núñez Alarcón H. Tropical plants to reduce chronic metabolic diseases in the obesity pandemic: a narrative review. *Academia Nutrition and Dietetics* 2025;2. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AcadNutr7702>

1. Introduction

Chronic metabolic diseases, including type 2 diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular disease, constitute a significant global health challenge [1]. In many regions, the prevalence of these conditions is rising, highlighting the urgent need for effective prevention strategies [2, 3]. Promoting healthy lifestyles and preventing chronic metabolic diseases are now central to global public health, underscoring the importance of research into functional foods. These foods have bioactive compounds to enhance metabolic health, offering a promising solution to combat these health issues [4].

The growing health and economic burden of chronic metabolic diseases highlights the importance of this approach, with a projected global loss of USD 17.3 trillion from 2011 to 2030 [5]. Tropical plants, with their rich botanical biodiversity, offer a unique opportunity to explore edible species with therapeutic potential [6].

Tropical plants are rich in bioactive compounds that show promise in modulating the risk of chronic metabolic diseases [7]. This study reviews the potential of functional foods for chronic disease risk reduction by examining bioactive compounds in tropical plants and relevant evidence. Understanding the specific bioactive compounds in these plants will aid in developing dietary interventions and public health strategies to improve metabolic health.

Employing a narrative review approach allows for a comprehensive integration and analysis of the existing literature, addressing the growing interest in functional foods and their role in metabolic disease risk reduction. Our review offers an updated perspective on plant-based functional foods, bioactive compounds, and metabolic health. It addresses the need to characterize local bioactive compounds and supports sustainable, regionally relevant nutrition solutions.

2. Materials and methods

A search of PubMed, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and Google Scholar identified clinical studies on tropical plants as functional foods for reducing the risk of chronic metabolic diseases, focusing on the past decade, in English and Spanish using keywords like (functional foods) AND (chronic metabolic disease) AND (cardiovascular disease) AND (diabetes) AND (obesity). The review highlighted ten tropical plants selected based on their high polyphenol or flavonoid content, substantial recent scientific evidence, and ethnobotanical relevance or well-documented traditional use. The analysis focused on their bioactive compositions and potential

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effectiveness in modulating metabolic risk factors for chronic diseases, particularly in relation to metabolic health outcomes.

Although flavonoids are a subclass of polyphenols, they were analyzed separately in this review due to their distinct chemical structure, specific mechanisms of action, and unique bioavailability. Unlike other polyphenols, such as phenolic acids and stilbenes (e.g., resveratrol), which are primarily involved in epigenetic regulation, gut microbiota modulation, and nuclear receptor interactions, flavonoids possess a characteristic C6-C3-C6 backbone that allows them to modulate key cellular signaling pathways. Additionally, their bioavailability differs significantly, as flavonoids require intestinal and hepatic transformation to become bioactive, further justifying their independent discussion.

Inclusion criteria focused on peer-reviewed studies like scientific articles, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. Priority was given to robust designs—randomized controlled trials and prospective observational studies—with large, representative samples, excluding studies with weak methods, small samples, conflicts of interest, or outdated data.

3. Results

3.1. Definition and classification of functional foods according to the origin of their bioactives

Functional foods provide basic nutrients and bioactive compounds that benefit health beyond nutritional value [8]. Plant-based bioactive compounds interact with biological processes to produce beneficial health effects, reducing the risk of diseases like cardiovascular disease, obesity, and type 2 diabetes [9]. Functional foods are classified by the origin of their bioactive compounds: animal, plant, microbial, or synthetic [10] (Table 1). This review examines plant-derived bioactives, with an emphasis on tropical plants, and their potential role in modulating risk factors for chronic metabolic diseases.

Table 1 • Bioactives by source.

Source	Bioactive compounds
Animal	Omega-3 fatty acids
	Bioactive peptides
	Liposoluble vitamins
Plant	Polyphenols
	Flavonoids
	Phytosterols
	Dietary fiber
	Carotenoids
Microbial	Probiotics
	Prebiotics
Synthetics and derivatives	Fortified vitamins and minerals
	Functional additives
Marina	Omega-3 fatty acids
	Marine carotenoids
Fungal	Beta-glucan
	Ergosterol

3.1.1. Tropical plant bioactives and risk modulation in chronic metabolic disease

Tropical plants contain diverse bioactive compounds that offer significant health benefits [11]. Found in fruits, vegetables, herbs, and spices, these compounds modulate risk factors for chronic metabolic diseases [12]. Notable bioactives include polyphenols, flavonoids like quercetin, carotenoids, phytosterols, and stanols [13]. Plant bioactives reduce blood sugar levels, improve insulin sensitivity, promote weight loss, and lower the risk of cardiovascular diseases [14, 15]. Phytosterols and stanols in tropical plants lower LDL cholesterol, improve insulin sensitivity, and reduce type 2 diabetes risk [16]. Mango gallotannins support gut bacteria, reduce inflammation, and strengthen gut integrity [17]. Carotenoids in mango and papaya support cardiovascular health by neutralizing free radicals, reducing LDL oxidation, and improving endothelial function [18]. Prebiotic fibers in mango and yerba mate support gut microbiota, enhance short-chain fatty acids that improve gut health, and lower chronic disease risk [19]. Non-pharmacological approaches involving bioactives are gaining attention in response to the obesity crisis [20]. Recent studies support the role of these bioactives in important metabolic processes that can be key in the prevention of diseases [21] (Figure 1).

3.2. Tropical plants with potential for chronic disease risk reduction

3.2.1. Yerba mate (*Ilex paraguariensis*)

Yerba mate has notable anti-obesity effects due to its rich phytochemical composition, including polyphenols, xanthines (such as caffeine and theobromine), and triterpene saponins. These bioactives offer antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and cardioprotective effects in both preclinical and clinical studies [22]. Experimental evidence from in vivo animal models suggests that yerba mate supplementation reduces inflammation, inhibits adipocyte differentiation, and limits triglyceride storage [23]. Saponins support cholesterol reduction via enhanced bile acid elimination, and phenolic compounds appear to modulate energy metabolism by inhibiting lipogenesis, promoting lipolysis, and supporting the composition of the gut microbiota [24]. Chlorogenic acid, one of the key phenolic constituents, has been shown to inhibit adipogenesis and improve insulin sensitivity by mitigating oxidative stress and modulating glucose metabolism pathways [25]. Clinical and preclinical research confirms yerba mate’s anti-obesity effects, with human studies showing increased fat oxidation and thermogenesis in overweight participants [26]. In parallel, animal studies using high-fat diet models have consistently demonstrated reductions in body weight gain, visceral fat accumulation, and markers of metabolic dysfunction [27]. Yerba mate’s flavonoids and saponins have also exhibited antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities in various experimental settings [28]. Long-term supplementation may reduce visceral adiposity through mechanisms involving AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) activation, enhanced thermogenesis, and modulation of adipogenesis [29]. In conclusion, the available preclinical and clinical data support the potential of yerba mate bioactives to promote thermogenesis, inhibit adipogenesis, enhance lipolysis, and improve insulin sensitivity, thereby contributing to the management of obesity and related metabolic disorders.

Figure 1 • Biological action mechanisms of bioactive compounds in tropical plants. Summary of the primary bioactives of tropical plants and their mechanisms of action, which are linked to the modulation of risk factors for chronic metabolic diseases.

3.2.2. Amarantho (*Amaranthus cruentus*)

Amaranth, a species of the Amaranthaceae family, is valued for its nutritional and phytochemical properties and traditional food applications and is currently gaining attention for its functional food potential. Amaranth is rich in polyphenols like betalains (antioxidants and anti-inflammatories) and saponins (lower fat absorption and cholesterol). It also contains bioactive peptides with antihypertensive and antioxidant properties in preclinical models, supporting cardiovascular and metabolic health, as well as potential immune modulation [30].

A study on cinnamic and benzoic acid flavonoids from *Amaranthus cruentus* showed strong antioxidant activity, inhibition of diabetes- and hypertension-related enzymes, and improved glucose homeostasis, highlighting its therapeutic potential for metabolic disorders [31]. The plant also possesses a high-quality protein profile, including essential amino acids, along with phenolics and carotenoids, which have been associated with reduced oxidative stress and inflammatory markers in preclinical research. These effects may play a role in modulating risk factors associated with non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular disease, obesity, and type 2 diabetes [32]. These bioactive compounds emphasize its potential as a functional food for modulating risk factors associated with obesity and chronic metabolic diseases.

3.2.3. Mango (*Mangifera indica*)

Mango pulp is rich in carotenoids, vitamin C, and amino acids, providing antioxidant protection. Mango peel contains prebiotic fibers, phenolics, and flavonoids with antimicrobial, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory properties, while the seed offers antioxidants and dietary fiber [33]. Bioactives from mango leaves, particularly polyphenols and mangiferin, have been shown in experimental models to modulate molecular pathways related to obesity and chronic metabolic diseases [34]. Mango polyphenols influence lipid metabolism and body weight regulation through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. Research indicates these polyphenols can inhibit adipogenesis and promote lipolysis, reducing fat accumulation [35]. Carotenoids like beta-carotene contribute to

body weight regulation by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, influencing lipid metabolism-related gene expression, promoting fat oxidation, and decreasing adiposity. Mango dietary fiber, especially from peel and pulp, enhances satiety, aids weight management, and acts as a prebiotic, benefiting gut health and modulating inflammation and metabolic responses [36]. Mangiferin, a xanthone compound distributed throughout the mango plant, has shown promising antidiabetic and antioxidant effects by enhancing insulin sensitivity, regulating glucose and lipid metabolism, and reducing biomarkers associated with metabolic dysfunction [37, 38]. Mangiferin has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic effects [39]. Studies show mango's benefits for metabolic health, including smaller postprandial insulin increases and higher adiponectin levels, improved lipid and glucose metabolism, lower blood glucose levels, and better lipid profiles [40]. Mango peel extracts reduced adiposity and improved metabolic markers in obese females, showing potential for modulating obesity-related risk factors [41]. Mango bioactives like mangiferin, quercetin, and isoquercetin activate antioxidant enzymes and modulate inflammation pathways such as NF- κ B and COX-2, contributing to the modulation of metabolic diseases related to oxidative stress and inflammation [42].

3.2.4. Papaya (*Carica papaya*)

Papaya offers nutritional and therapeutic benefits [43]. Its seeds contain phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and oleic acid, which have been associated with cardiometabolic benefits, including lipid-lowering effects and improvements in glucose metabolism in preclinical models. These effects may support the management of cardiovascular risk factors and metabolic disorders such as type 2 diabetes and obesity [44]. Papaya leaves are rich in fiber, polyphenols, flavonoids, and saponins, protecting cells by reducing lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress [45]. Papaya contains papain, aiding protein digestion, metabolism, and weight regulation. Papain reduces inflammation by inhibiting Cox-2 expression and regulating MAPKs and PI3K/Akt pathways and optimizes nutrient utilization and reduces fat accumulation, with studies showing

significant reductions in body weight and improved lipid profiles in high-fat-fed rats [46]. Papaya juice has demonstrated the ability to inhibit pancreatic lipase activity in vitro, suggesting a mechanism through which it could influence lipid absorption and obesity-related parameters [47]. Hypoglycemic compounds in papaya improve insulin sensitivity and glycemic control. Fermented papaya protects erythrocytes from oxidative stress. Flavonoids such as kaempferol, quercetin, and ferulic acid may contribute to glucose uptake by upregulating GLUT4 expression [48]. Papaya's dietary fiber promotes satiety, regulates digestion, and aids weight management. Antioxidants and fiber reduce inflammation and oxidative stress, protecting against cardiovascular and metabolic diseases [49]. Fermented papaya benefits gut microbiota, acting as an antioxidant and preventing inflammation-related diseases like obesity and diabetes [50]. Papaya offers diverse health benefits, contributing to cardiovascular health, metabolic efficiency, weight regulation, and improved glycemic control, making it a promising natural approach for reducing the risk of and managing chronic metabolic diseases.

3.2.5. Guayaba (*Psidium guajava*)

Guava is rich in beneficial phytochemicals with antioxidant, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, antidiarrheal, and lipid-lowering properties [51]. These bioactives support the maintenance of metabolic health and help counteract the development of conditions like type 2 diabetes and obesity [52]. Guava leaves contain phenolic compounds and flavonoids that protect cells from oxidative damage by neutralizing free radicals and activating antioxidant pathways, thereby reducing oxidative stress and limiting fat accumulation—key mechanisms in the modulation of obesity-related risk factors. Additionally, phytosterols in guava seed oil help lower plasma triglycerides [53]. Aqueous extracts of guava leaves improve insulin sensitivity and glucose regulation. Compounds like quercetin and chlorogenic acid inhibit enzymes, reducing glucose absorption and enhancing insulin signaling by increasing GLUT4 expression. Studies in diabetic rats show that guava leaf extract reduces oxidative stress, regulates insulin signaling pathways in skeletal muscle, and upregulates insulin signaling genes, suggesting its potential for diabetes treatment [54]. Guava leaf extract inhibits adipogenesis, improves adipocyte function by decreasing basal lipolysis, and increases insulin-induced glucose uptake. By inhibiting adipogenic transcription factors, it reduces lipid accumulation during adipocyte differentiation and suppresses mitotic clonal expansion, suggesting potential for improving adipocyte function and metabolic regulation [55]. The integration of these molecular and cellular effects contributes to the observed antidiabetic and hepatoprotective actions of guava extracts in preclinical research, improving adipocyte function and regulating glucose and lipid levels in the body. Guava shows great potential for managing chronic metabolic diseases and modulating their underlying risk factors.

3.2.6. Piña (*Ananas comosus*)

Pineapple, a tropical plant of the Bromeliaceae family, is an excellent source of fiber and bioactives such as bromelain, gallic acid, catechin, epicatechin, ferulic acid, quercetin, avicularin, and apigenin, which improve lipid profiles, cardiac oxidative stress, and inflammation, as well as volatile antioxidant compounds like isopentyl and ethyl acetate, which may contribute to the prevention of metabolic disorders [56].

Bromelain, a proteolytic enzyme from the fruit and stem, has potent anti-inflammatory properties by modulating the arachidonic acid system and inhibiting platelet aggregation, highlighting its therapeutic potential in preventing thrombotic events and managing chronic inflammatory disorders. These actions suggest a potential role in preventing thrombotic events and managing chronic inflammation; however, most of these effects have been demonstrated in preclinical settings, and further clinical trials are needed to confirm its efficacy and safety in human populations [57]. Pineapple juice reduces body weight, BMI, body fat, liver fat, and blood lipids in high-fat diet animal models by affecting genes involved in lipogenesis, lipolysis, and glucose transport [58]. Pineapple leaf extract also shows anti-inflammatory potential by inhibiting protein denaturation, protease activity, and reducing pro-inflammatory cytokines, useful for treating acute inflammatory conditions [59]. Overall, the bioactive compounds in pineapple and its by-products may offer health benefits related to cardiovascular and metabolic regulation, mainly through antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and lipid/glucose metabolism-modulating mechanisms. However, as the majority of current evidence stems from in vitro and animal studies, further well-designed human clinical trials are necessary to substantiate these potential therapeutic applications.

3.2.7. Araticum (*Annona crassiflora*)

Annona crassiflora, known as araticum, contains bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, and carotenoids in its fruit, peel, and seeds, exhibiting antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and antimicrobial effects. Among these, catechin and epicatechin are the predominant phenolic constituents, with the peel demonstrating the highest concentration of total phenolics and antioxidant activity [60]. Preclinical studies have highlighted araticum's antioxidant and lipid-lowering effects. In hyperlipidemic animal models, administration of fruit peel extracts significantly improved plasma antioxidant capacity, reduced serum lipid levels, and exhibited hepatoprotective effects [61]. Treatment with an *Annona crassiflora*-enriched fraction elevated glutathione levels, decreased superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase activity, increased total antioxidant capacity, and decreased oxidative stress markers such as protein carbonylation and lipid peroxidation [62]. The bioactive compounds of *Annona crassiflora*, particularly its procyanidins, possess strong antioxidant and anti-glycation properties. By inhibiting the formation of advanced glycation end-products and reducing oxidative stress, they may help lower the risk of chronic metabolic diseases such as type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease [63]. In summary, *Annona crassiflora* offers health benefits due to its rich bioactive composition, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative, and wound-healing properties, with potential in modulating metabolic risk factors associated with metabolic disorders driven by oxidative stress and chronic inflammation.

3.2.8. Stevia (*Stevia rebaudiana*)

Stevia rebaudiana, known as stevia, is a plant native to Paraguay called ka'a he'ê in Guarani, meaning "sweet herb". It is an alternative to sugar due to its natural sweetening properties and low calorie content. Stevia contains bioactive compounds like steviol, stevioside, and rebaudioside A, which have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, and cardioprotective effects.

Studies show that *Stevia rebaudiana* leaf aqueous extract has high antioxidant activity, inhibiting hydroxyl radicals, nitric oxide, and superoxide anions due to its phenolic content [64]. Steviol glycosides protect against oxidative damage, support the vascular endothelium, and reduce atherosclerosis risk by decreasing reactive oxygen species and increasing antioxidant capacity. They help reduce chronic inflammation, a risk factor for metabolic and cardiovascular diseases [65]. In animal and human studies, steviol glycosides have exhibited antihypertensive effects, particularly in reducing systolic blood pressure, without significantly altering body mass index (BMI), diastolic pressure, or lipid and glucose profiles. Clinical trials have also indicated that stevia intake may contribute to reduced caloric consumption and stable glycemic responses in healthy adults, suggesting metabolic neutrality with potential weight management benefits [66]. Stevia leaves are also a source of chlorogenic acids—phenolic esters known for their potent antioxidant properties—which may offer additional protection against oxidative damage and contribute to its therapeutic potential [67]. Mechanistically, stevia exerts its cardiometabolic effects through vasodilatory actions, ACE (angiotensin-converting enzyme) inhibition, anti-inflammatory pathways, and free radical scavenging [68]. Despite promising preclinical and clinical findings, further large-scale, randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm the long-term efficacy and safety of *S. rebaudiana* and its derivatives in the management of chronic metabolic and cardiovascular conditions. Nevertheless, current evidence supports its role as a functional food ingredient with the potential to modulate key risk factors associated with hypertension, obesity, and insulin resistance.

3.2.9. Maracuya (*Passiflora edulis*)

Passiflora edulis, or passion fruit, contains bioactive compounds with numerous health benefits, including antioxidant, antihypertensive, sedative, antidiabetic, anti-glycation, and anti-inflammatory properties. Several studies have reported that specific extracts from *P. edulis* exhibit antiglucagon activity, which may contribute to improved glycemic control [69]. Flavonoids like vitexin and isovitexin contribute to vascular relaxation, lowering blood pressure and alleviating stress and anxiety [70]. Recent studies identified flavonoids such as orientin and isorientin in peel extracts, alongside pectin in aqueous extracts, showing significant vasorelaxing effects through potassium channel activation. These effects have been corroborated in preclinical models, where the extracts enhanced insulin sensitivity and exerted hypoglycemic activity in rats with type 2 diabetes [71]. In diabetic mice, a polysaccharide from *Passiflora edulis* peel showed hypoglycemic effects, reduced weight gain and blood glucose levels, improved glucose and insulin tolerance, and increased antioxidant enzyme activity. Changes in short-chain fatty acids positively influence systemic inflammation and insulin resistance, improving metabolic responses and reducing chronic disease risks [72]. Ethanol extracts of passion fruit seeds, particularly those high in piceatannol, have

shown potent antidiabetic, anti-glycation, and antioxidant effects. Mechanistically, these compounds inhibit key enzymes involved in carbohydrate digestion, such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase, and reduce the formation of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs), thus mitigating hyperglycemia-induced oxidative damage [73]. Leaf extracts, high in flavonoids and saponins, exhibit anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting nitric oxide synthase [74]. Collectively, the evidence from both in vitro and in vivo studies supports the therapeutic potential of *Passiflora edulis* as a source of functional compounds for the prevention and management of chronic metabolic diseases, including type 2 diabetes, hypertension, and inflammatory disorders.

3.2.10. Ñangapiri (*Eugenia uniflora*)

Eugenia uniflora, known as ñangapirí, pitanga, or Surinam cherry, is native to tropical South America, including Paraguay, Brazil, Argentina, and Uruguay. It belongs to the Myrtaceae family and is recognized for its edible fruits. The phytochemical profile of *Eugenia uniflora* includes flavonoids such as myricetin and quercetin, which exhibit anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antidiabetic properties [75]. Phytochemical analysis of the leaves has led to the identification of 22 secondary metabolites, many of which exhibit potent free radical scavenging capacity in vitro [76]. Research on an animal model of metabolic syndrome investigated the effects of *Eugenia uniflora* red fruit extract. Findings indicated that the extract reduced oxidative damage, improved antioxidant markers, and mitigated metabolic changes such as glucose intolerance and increased visceral fat, linked to the presence of nine major anthocyanins [77]. Mechanistic insights reveal that *E. uniflora* exerts antioxidant effects by preserving intracellular glutathione levels and enhancing the activity of superoxide dismutase, while concurrently downregulating the expression of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS). These changes contribute to decreased production of reactive nitrogen species and improved redox balance [78]. Additionally, the extract shows hepatoprotective potential by reducing oxidative liver damage through lipid peroxidation reduction and increased endogenous antioxidant enzymes [79]. Overall, *Eugenia uniflora* presents a promising resource for treating and preventing metabolic and cardiovascular diseases due to its diverse health benefits, including metabolic disorder prevention, oxidative damage protection, and anti-inflammatory properties.

To summarize the main findings, an overview is provided of the selected tropical plants, their primary bioactives, mechanisms of action, and the type of evidence supporting their metabolic health benefits. Additionally, recently published studies have been included to strengthen the scientific support for each plant listed in **Table 2**.

Following the summary in **Table 2**, **Figure 2a,b** offer a visual representation of the connections between selected tropical plants, their main bioactive compounds, and their potential effects on metabolic health.

Table 2 • Bioactive compounds, mechanisms of action, and target disease of selected tropical plants. The target disease for each plant was selected based on the number of published studies linking it to a specific chronic metabolic condition, prioritizing the most relevant and scientifically robust references.

Plant	Key bioactives	Mechanisms of action	Study type	Target disease	Reference
Yerba Mate (<i>Ilex paraguariensis</i>)	Chlorogenic acid, flavonoids, xanthines, saponins	Stimulates thermogenesis via AMPK	Clinical trials and preclinical studies	Obesity and metabolic syndrome	[80–82]

Table 2 • Cont.

Plant	Key bioactives	Mechanisms of action	Study type	Target disease	Reference
Amaranth (<i>Amaranthus cruentus</i>)	Betalains, saponins, peptides	Lowers oxidation and inflammation	Preclinical and in vitro	Obesity and metabolic disorders	[83]
Mango (<i>Mangifera indica</i>)	Mangiferin, quercetin, isoquercetin, beta-carotene	Modulates lipid oxidative stress and inflammation	Clinical and preclinical	Obesity and T2D	[84–86]
Papaya (<i>Carica papaya</i>)	Papain, quercetin, kaempferol, ferulic acid, carotenoids	Improving glycemic and lipid metabolism	Preclinical and clinical	Obesity, T2D, and CVD	[87, 88]
Guava (<i>Psidium guajava</i>)	Phenolics, flavonoids (quercetin, chlorogenic acid), phytosterols	Enhances insulin signaling via GLUT4 upregulation and adipogenesis inhibition	In vivo (diabetic rats)	Obesity and T2D	[89–92]
Pineapple (<i>Ananas comosus</i>)	Bromelain, phenolic acids, quercetin, apigenin, avicularin	Downregulates lipogenic genes	In vivo (high-fat diet animal models)	Obesity and cardiovascular disease	[93]
Araticum (<i>Annona crassiflora</i>)	catechins, procyanidins, flavonoids, carotenoids, alkaloids	Inhibits AGEs and oxidative stress	In vivo (preclinical models)	T2D	[94–96]
Stevia (<i>Stevia rebaudiana</i>)	Steviol glycosides	Reduces intake and maintains weight without impacting glucose	Human clinical study	Obesity/metabolic syndrome	[97, 98]
Maracuyá (<i>Passiflora edulis</i>)	Piceatannol, polysaccharides	Inhibits α -amylase/ α -glucosidase and AGEs formation	In vivo (diabetic mice models)	Type 2 diabetes	[99, 100]
Ñangapirí (<i>Eugenia uniflora</i>)	Myricetin, quercetin, glutathione	Reduces inflammation by inhibiting nitric oxide synthase	In vivo (animal model)	Inflammatory diseases	[101]

The table highlights key abbreviations: T2D for type 2 diabetes, CVD for cardiovascular disease, GLUT4 for glucose uptake into cells, AMPK for maintaining energy balance, and AGEs for harmful glycation end-products.

(a)

Figure 2 • Cont.

(b)

Figure 2 • (a) Visual summary of bioactive compounds and their health benefits in selected tropical plants. The image shows key bioactive compounds in five tropical plants and their health benefits, such as reducing inflammation and improving insulin sensitivity. **(b)** Visual summary of bioactive compounds and their health benefits in selected tropical plants. The image shows key bioactive compounds from five plants and their health benefits, highlighting their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardiovascular, and metabolic health-enhancing properties.

4. Discussion

Our narrative review emphasizes the promising role of tropical plants as key functional foods in the modulation of risk factors associated with chronic metabolic diseases. In the context of the global rise in type 2 diabetes, obesity, hypertension, and cardiovascular diseases, dietary strategies focused on prevention and metabolic regulation are becoming increasingly essential. Tropical plants are particularly rich in bioactive compounds such as polyphenols (e.g., chlorogenic acid and quercetin), flavonoids (e.g., kaempferol and rutin), carotenoids (e.g., β -carotene and lutein), alkaloids (e.g., mateine and theobromine), and phenolic acids (e.g., caffeic and ferulic acids), which exert multifaceted effects on metabolic health. These compounds modulate key cellular pathways, including AMPK activation, NF- κ B inhibition, and PPAR signaling, contributing to improved insulin sensitivity, lipid metabolism, and anti-inflammatory responses [102]. Compared to more commonly studied functional foods such as green tea, berries, or oats, many tropical plants demonstrate comparable or even superior concentrations of bioactives with broader ethnopharmacological relevance [103]. For example, yerba mate (*Ilex paraguariensis*) exhibits strong antioxidant and lipid-lowering properties, while guava leaves (*Psidium guajava*) have shown potent α -glucosidase inhibitory effects, beneficial in glycemic control. This biochemical richness, combined with traditional knowledge and

underexplored biodiversity, positions tropical plants as uniquely valuable in the global strategy to combat chronic metabolic diseases [104].

A crucial aspect that we highlight is the effect of bioactive compounds on the intestinal microbiota, an ecosystem that regulates numerous metabolic functions. Its dysbiosis has been associated with the development of chronic metabolic diseases. Several of the bioactives present in the plants studied, such as phenolic acids and flavonoids, act as prebiotics, promoting the growth of beneficial bacteria that produce short-chain fatty acids, which are essential for the improvement in insulin sensitivity and the reduction in inflammation [105]. Despite positive evidence, critical issues limit result interpretation. Many studies lack large-scale, controlled clinical trials, making extrapolation to humans difficult. Evidence from animal models limits generalizability. Variability in study design, bioactive compound characterization, and short study durations pose additional challenges. The limited number of studies on the bioavailability of bioactive compounds and the scarcity of large-scale, randomized controlled clinical trials in humans restrict evidence-based nutritional recommendations.

This review aligns with a growing body of international research highlighting the ability of plant-derived bioactive compounds to modulate key metabolic processes involved in chronic disease

development. For instance, a clinical study demonstrated that a polyphenol-rich extract significantly reduced blood glucose levels and improved glucose tolerance in individuals with prediabetes or early-stage type 2 diabetes, underscoring the regulatory role of polyphenols on insulin signaling and glucose metabolism. Beyond polyphenols, tropical plants are abundant in flavonoids such as quercetin and rutin, which have been shown to inhibit α -glucosidase and enhance GLUT4 translocation, thereby improving postprandial glycemic control [106]. Compared to widely recognized functional foods like green tea, turmeric, or blueberries, many tropical species contain a more diverse and concentrated array of bioactives acting on multiple targets simultaneously. For example, Amaranth not only exhibits antioxidant activity through Nrf2 pathway activation but also demonstrates hypolipidemic effects by modulating PPAR- α expression [107]. Similarly, alkaloids found in yerba mate, including caffeine and small amounts of theobromine and theophylline, contribute to increased energy expenditure and fat oxidation, distinguishing these plants from traditional sources with more limited mechanisms. This multifunctional bioactivity highlights the unique therapeutic potential of tropical biodiversity in addressing complex metabolic dysregulation [108].

In this regard, and in the local context, yerba mate (*Ilex paraguariensis*) has been the subject of studies that suggest its ability to improve lipid profiles and insulin sensitivity. However, although international studies have shown its potential to reduce inflammation and free radical production, research on other less studied plants, such as *Eugenia uniflora*, is limited.

For public health and preventive medicine, the results of this review could have important implications. The tropical plants that have been reviewed represent an accessible source of functional foods that could be incorporated into preventive strategies at the level of the individual and the community. Including these foods in the daily diet could not only improve the quality of life of the population, but also reduce the economic burden associated with the medical care of chronic diseases. Moreover, these findings underscore the urgent need to preserve the biodiversity of tropical plants, given their high potential for promoting health and preventing disease, making them invaluable to public health efforts now and in the future.

Validating observed effects requires randomized clinical trials. Future research should explore bioactive synergies and mechanisms, while promoting culturally acceptable and accessible food development. This review underscores the potential of tropical plants to reduce the risk of chronic metabolic diseases, while emphasizing the need for more rigorous future studies. Multi-sectoral collaboration and public policies supporting research and consumption are critical for improving public health and managing metabolic disease epidemics.

5. Conclusions

This narrative review highlights the potential of bioactive compounds found in ten tropical plants—yerba mate, Amaranth, mango, papaya, guava, pineapple, *Araticum*, stevia, passion fruit, and *Eugenia uniflora*—as functional foods capable of modulating risk factors associated with chronic metabolic diseases. These plants exhibit a remarkable diversity of phytochemicals with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and cardioprotective

properties, which act through complementary mechanisms to support metabolic and cardiovascular health. Yerba mate provides polyphenols, xanthines, and saponins that activate AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), inhibit adipogenesis, and promote thermogenesis, thus supporting weight management. Amaranth contributes betalains, saponins, and peptides that enhance glucose homeostasis, reduce cholesterol, and limit fat absorption. Mango is a rich source of mangiferin, carotenoids, polyphenols, and dietary fiber, which collectively promote insulin sensitivity, lipid regulation, and gut health. Papaya offers papain, carotenoids, phenolics, and fiber that aid digestion, promote satiety, and reduce inflammation and lipid accumulation. Guava delivers quercetin, flavonoids, and phytosterols that regulate glucose and lipid metabolism while protecting hepatic function and preventing adipogenesis. Pineapple contains bromelain, catechins, and gallic acid, compounds that reduce inflammation, modulate glucose and lipid profiles, and support cardiovascular health. *Araticum*, rich in polyphenols, catechin, and carotenoids, helps inhibit the formation of advanced glycation end-products and modulate inflammatory pathways, contributing to metabolic stability. Stevia's steviol glycosides offer antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antihypertensive effects that support vascular health and glycemic control. Passion fruit provides vitexin, isovitexin, and piceatannol, which improve insulin sensitivity, lower blood pressure, and reduce systemic inflammation. *Eugenia uniflora* contributes myricetin and quercetin, flavonoids that enhance antioxidant defenses, reduce fat accumulation, and improve glucose metabolism. Taken together, these tropical plants represent a powerful natural strategy for reducing the risk of and managing chronic diseases such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular conditions. Current evidence suggests that regular consumption of these functional foods may be an effective, accessible, and affordable approach to improving public health outcomes. However, additional controlled, long-term clinical trials are necessary to validate their efficacy and mechanisms in humans. Beyond their potential health benefits, promoting the integration of these plants into daily diets also supports agricultural sustainability and the conservation of tropical biodiversity. Their phytochemical richness represents not only a valuable ecological heritage but also a strategic resource for future therapeutic innovation. Preserving and studying this biodiversity is essential for advancing global health equity and ensuring that these natural resources continue to benefit populations now and in the future.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to the Universidad del Pacífico, Asunción, Paraguay, for their valuable assistance in conducting this study.

Funding

There are no sources of funding to declare.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, M.A.F.; methodology, M.A.F.; formal analysis, H.N.A.; writing—original draft preparation, M.A.F. and H.N.A.; writing—review and editing, M.A.F. Both authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability statement

Data supporting these findings are available within the article, at <https://doi.org/10.20935/AcadNutr7702>, or upon request.

Institutional review board statement

Not applicable.

Informed consent statement

Not applicable.

Additional information

Received: 2024-11-26

Accepted: 2025-04-22

Published: 2025-05-21

Academia Nutrition and Dietetics papers should be cited as *Academia Nutrition and Dietetics 2025*, ISSN 3067-1345, <https://doi.org/10.20935/AcadNutr7702>. The journal's official abbreviation is *Acad. Nutri.*

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References

- Chew NWS, Ng CH, Tan DJH, Kong G, Lin C, Chin YH, et al. The global burden of metabolic disease: data from 2000 to 2019. *Cell Metabolism*. 2023;35(3):414–28.e3. doi: 10.1016/j.cmet.2023.02.003
- Chooi YC, Ding C, Magkos F. The epidemiology of obesity. *Metabolism*. 2019;92:6–10. doi: 10.1016/j.metabol.2018.09.005
- Pizuorno A, Fierro NA. Latin America and chronic diseases: a perfect storm during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Ann Hepatol*. 2021;22:100332. doi: 10.1016/j.aohep.2021.100332
- De Brito Alves JL, Souza ELD. Functional foods with modulating action on metabolic risk factors. *Foods*. 2023;12(21):4043. doi: 10.3390/foods12214043
- Chong B, Jayabaskaran J, Kong G, Chan YH, Chin YH, Goh R, et al. Trends and predictions of malnutrition and obesity in 204 countries and territories: an analysis of the global burden of disease study 2019. *eClinicalMedicine*. 2023;57:101850. doi: 10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.101850
- Marchi P, Bauer F, Cacciali P, Yanosky A, Dujak M, Dujak C, et al. Biodiversity in Paraguay: selected countries in the Americas and Australia. *Glob Biodivers*. 2018;4:339–78. doi: 10.1201/9780429433634-9
- De Arrúa RLD, González Y, Ferro BEA. Ethnobotanical issues on medicinal plants from Paraguay. In: *Ethnobotany*. Boca Raton (FL): CRC Press; 2019. doi: 10.1201/9780429424069-12
- Temple NJ. A rational definition for functional foods: a perspective. *Front Nutr*. 2022;9:957516. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2022.957516
- Santos-Buelga C, González-Paramás AM, Oludemi T, Ayuda-Durán B, González-Manzano S. Plant phenolics as functional food ingredients. *Adv Food Nutr Res*. 2019;90:183–257. doi: 10.1016/bs.afnr.2019.02.012
- Martirosyan D, Ekblad M. Functional foods classification system: exemplifying through analysis of bioactive compounds. *Funct Food Sci*. 2022;2(4):94. doi: 10.31989/ffs.v2i4.919
- Kussmann M, Abe Cunha DH, Berciano S. Bioactive compounds for human and planetary health. *Front Nutr*. 2023; 10:1193848. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2023.1193848
- Sayago-Ayerdi S, García-Martínez DL, Ramírez-Castillo AC, Ramírez-Concepción HR, Viuda-Martos M. Tropical fruits and their co-products as bioactive compounds and their health effects: a review. *Foods*. 2021;10(8):1952. doi: 10.3390/foods10081952
- Samtiya M, Aluko RE, Dhewa T, Moreno-Rojas JM. Potential health benefits of plant food-derived bioactive components: an overview. *Foods*. 2021;10(4):839. doi: 10.3390/foods10040839
- Morand C, Tomás-Barberán FA. Contribution of plant food bioactives in promoting health effects of plant foods: why look at interindividual variability? *Eur J Nutr*. 2019;58(Suppl 2):13–9. doi: 10.1007/s00394-019-02096-0
- Milenkovic D, Morand C, Cassidy A, Konic-Ristic A, Tomás-Barberán F, Ordovas JM, et al. Interindividual variability in biomarkers of cardiometabolic health after consumption of major plant-food bioactive compounds and the determinants involved. *Adv Nutr*. 2017;8(4):558–70. doi: 10.3945/an.116.013623
- Wang Y, Alkhalidy H, Liu D. The emerging role of polyphenols in the management of type 2 diabetes. *Molecules*. 2021;26(3):703. doi: 10.3390/molecules26030703

17. Kim H, Castellon-Chicas MJ, Arbizu S, Talcott ST, Drury NL, Smith S, et al. Mango [*Mangifera indica* L.] polyphenols: anti-inflammatory intestinal microbial health benefits, and associated mechanisms of actions. *Molecules*. 2021;26(9):2732. doi: 10.3390/molecules26092732
18. Bhatt T, Patel K. Carotenoids: potent to prevent diseases review. *Nat Prod Bioprospect*. 2020;10(3):109–17. doi: 10.1007/s13659-020-00244-2
19. Kaur AP, Bhardwaj S, Dhanjal DS, Nepovimova E, Cruz-Martins N, Kuča K, et al. Plant prebiotics and their role in the amelioration of diseases. *Biomolecules*. 2021;11(3):440. doi: 10.3390/biom11030440
20. Tak YJ, Lee SY. Long-term efficacy and safety of anti-obesity treatment: where do we stand? *Curr Obes Rep*. 2021;10(1):14–30. doi: 10.1007/s13679-020-00422-w
21. Manríquez-Núñez J, Ramos-Gómez M. Bioactive compounds and adipocyte browning phenomenon. *Curr Issues Mol Biol*. 2022;44(7):3039–52. doi: 10.3390/cimb44070210
22. Rodríguez-Pérez C, Segura-Carretero A, Del Mar Contreras M. Phenolic compounds as natural and multifunctional anti-obesity agents: a review. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*. 2019;59(8):1212–29. doi: 10.1080/10408398.2017.1399859
23. Gambero A, Ribeiro ML. The positive effects of yerba maté [*Ilex paraguariensis*] in obesity. *Nutrients*. 2015;7(2):730–50. doi: 10.3390/nu7020730
24. Valença HDM, Silva CPE, De Brito Gitirana L, Valença SS, Lanzetti M. Beneficial effects of *Ilex paraguariensis* in the prevention of obesity-associated metabolic disorders in mice. *Phytother Res*. 2022;36(2):1032–42. doi: 10.1002/ptr.7377
25. De Vasconcellos AC, Frazzon J, Zapata Noreña CP. Phenolic compounds present in yerba mate potentially increase human health: a critical review. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr*. 2022;77(4):495–503. doi: 10.1007/s11130-022-01008-8
26. Kim SY, Oh MR, Kim MG, Chae HJ, Chae SW. Anti-obesity effects of yerba mate [*Ilex Paraguariensis*]: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial. *BMC Complement Altern Med*. 2015;15(1):338. doi: 10.1186/s12906-015-0859-1
27. Choi MS, Park HJ, Kim SR, Kim DY, Jung UJ. Long-term dietary supplementation with yerba mate ameliorates diet-induced obesity and metabolic disorders in mice by regulating energy expenditure and lipid metabolism. *J Med Food*. 2017;20(12):1168–75. doi: 10.1089/jmf.2017.3995
28. Paluch E, Okińczyc P, Zwyrzykowska-Wodzińska A, Szperlik J, Żarowska B, Duda-Madej A, et al. Composition and antimicrobial activity of *Ilex* leaves water extracts. *Molecules*. 2021;26(24):7442. doi: 10.3390/molecules26247442
29. Jung JH, Hur YI. The Effect of maté extract on body weight and fat reduction in obese women: a randomized placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Korean J Obes*. 2016;25(4):197–206. doi: 10.7570/kjo.2016.25.4.197
30. Soriano-García M, Ilnamiqui Arias-Olguín I, Pablo Carrillo Montes J, Genaro Rosas Ramírez D, Silvestre Mendoza Figueroa J, Flores-Valverde E, et al. Nutritional functional value and therapeutic utilization of Amaranth. *J Anal Pharm Res*. 2018;7(5):590–600. doi: 10.15406/japlr.2018.07.00288
31. Araujo-León JA, Sánchez-del Pino I, Ortiz-Andrade R, Hidalgo-Figueroa S, Carrera-Lanestosa A, Brito-Argáez LG, et al. HPLC-based metabolomic analysis and characterization of *Amaranthus cruentus* leaf and inflorescence extracts for their antidiabetic and antihypertensive potential. *Molecules*. 2024;29(9):2003. doi: 10.3390/molecules29092003
32. Jamka M, Morawska A, Krzyżanowska-Jankowska P, Bajerska J, Przysławski J, Walkowiak J, et al. Comparison of the effect of amaranth oil vs. rapeseed oil on selected atherosclerosis markers in overweight and obese subjects: a randomized double-blind cross-over trial. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(16):8540. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18168540
33. Lebaka VR, Wee YJ, Ye W, Korivi M. Nutritional composition and bioactive compounds in three different parts of mango fruit. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(2):741. doi: 10.3390/ijerph18020741
34. Kumar M, Saurabh V, Tomar M, Hasan M, Changan S, Sasi M, et al. Mango [*Mangifera indica* L.] leaves: nutritional composition, phytochemical profile, and health-promoting bioactivities. *Antioxidants*. 2021;10(2):299. doi: 10.3390/antiox10020299
35. Fang C, Kim H, Barnes RC, Talcott ST, Mertens-Talcott SU. Obesity-associated diseases biomarkers are differently modulated in lean and obese individuals and inversely correlated to plasma polyphenolic metabolites after 6 weeks of mango [*Mangifera indica* L.] consumption. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. 2018;62(14):1800129. doi: 10.1002/mnfr.201800129
36. Pinneo S, O’Mealy C, Rosas M Jr., Tsang M, Castro R, Sagisi S, et al. Effects of fresh mango fruit consumption on glucose, insulin and satiety hormones. *Curr Dev Nutr*. 2020;4:nzaa045_086. doi: 10.1089/jmf.2021.0063
37. Stamper C, Safadi S, Gehr A, Asuncion P, Hong MY. Effects of fresh vs dried mango consumption on satiety and postprandial glucose in healthy adults. *Metabolism Open*. 2023;19:100253. doi: 10.1016/j.metop.2023.100253
38. Rosas M Jr., Pinneo S, O’Mealy C, Liu C, Kern M, Hooshmand S, et al. Effects of fresh mango consumption on blood glucose, insulin, and other cardiovascular disease risk factors in overweight and obese adults. *Curr Dev Nutr*. 2021;5:366. doi: 10.1016/j.numecd.2021.11.001
39. Ahmad R, Alqathama A, Aldholmi M, Riaz M, Abdalla AN, Aljishi F, et al. Antidiabetic and anticancer potentials of *Mangifera indica* L. from different geographical origins. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2023;16(3):350. doi: 10.3390/ph16030350

40. Pinneo S, O'Mealy C, Rosas M Jr., Tsang M, Liu C, Kern M, et al. Fresh mango consumption promotes greater satiety and improves postprandial glucose and insulin responses in healthy overweight and obese adults. *J Med Food*. 2022;25(4):381–8. doi: 10.1089/jmf.2021.0063
41. Arshad F, Umbreen H, Aslam I, Hameed A, Aftab K, Al-Qahtani WH, et al. Therapeutic role of mango peels in management of dyslipidemia and oxidative stress in obese females. *BioMed Res Int*. 2021;2021:3094571. doi: 10.1155/2021/3094571
42. Dutta T, Das T, Gopalakrishnan AV, Saha SC, Ghorai M, Nandy S, et al. Mangiferin: the miraculous xanthone with diverse pharmacological properties. *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol*. 2023;396(5):851–63. doi: 10.1007/s00210-022-02373-6
43. Adeoye RI, Olopade ET, Olayemi IO, Okaiyeto K, Akiibinu MO. Nutritional and therapeutic potentials of *Carica papaya* Linn. seed: a comprehensive review. *Plant Sci Today*. 2024;11(2):671–80. doi: 10.14719/pst.2843
44. Santana LF, Inada AC, Espirito Santo BLSD, Filiú WFO, Pott A, Alves FM, et al. Nutraceutical potential of *Carica papaya* in metabolic syndrome. *Nutrients*. 2019;11(7):1608. doi: 10.3390/nu11071608
45. Yap JY, Hii CL, Ong SP, Lim KH, Abas F, Pin KY. Effects of drying on total polyphenols content and antioxidant properties of *Carica papaya* leaves. *J Sci Food Agric*. 2020;100(7):2932–7. doi: 10.1002/jsfa.10320
46. OdEk P, Deenin W, Malakul W, Phoungpetchara I, Tun-sophon S. Antiobesity effect of *Carica papaya* in high-fat diet fed rats. *Biomed Rep*. 2020;13:30. doi: 10.3892/br.2020.1337
47. Pandey S, Cabot PJ, Shaw PN, Hewavitharana AK. Anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties of *Carica papaya*. *J Immunotoxicol*. 2016;13(4):590–602. doi: 10.3109/1547691X.2016.1149528
48. Roy JR, Janaki CS, Jayaraman S, Periyasamy V, Balaji T, Vijayamalathi M, et al. *Carica papaya* reduces muscle insulin resistance via IR/GLUT4 mediated signaling mechanisms in high fat diet and streptozotocin-induced type-2 diabetic rats. *Antioxidants*. 2022;11(10):2081. doi: 10.3390/antiox11102081
49. Jeon YA, Chung SW, Kim SC, Lee YJ. Comprehensive assessment of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of papaya extracts. *Foods*. 2022;11(20):3211. doi: 10.3390/foods11203211
50. Leitão M, Ribeiro T, García PA, Barreiros L, Correia P. Benefits of fermented papaya in human health. *Foods*. 2022;11(4):563. doi: 10.3390/foods11040563
51. Pereira GA, Chaves DSDA, Silva TME, Motta REDA, Silva ABRD, Patricio TCDC, et al. Antimicrobial activity of psidium guajava aqueous extract against sensitive and resistant bacterial strains. *Microorganisms*. 2023;11(7):1784. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms11071784
52. Sharma S, Borah DRA. Bioactive compounds present in different parts of Guava and their significance: a review. *Pharma Innovation*. 2021;10(5):163–71. doi: 10.22271/tpi.2021.v10.i5c.6193
53. Prommaban A, Utama-ang N, Chaikitwattana A, Uthai-pibull C, Porter JB, Srichairatanakool S. Phytosterol, lipid and phenolic composition, and biological activities of guava seed oil. *Molecules*. 2020;25(11):2474. doi: 10.3390/molecules25112474
54. Jayachandran M, Vinayagam R, Xu B. Guava leaves extract ameliorates STZ induced diabetes mellitus via activation of PI3K/AKT signaling in skeletal muscle of rats. *Mol Biol Rep*. 2020;47(4):2793–9. doi: 10.1007/s11033-020-05399-2
55. Choi E, Baek S, Baek K, Kim HK. Psidium guajava L. leaf extract inhibits adipocyte differentiation and improves insulin sensitivity in 3T3-L1 cells. *Nutr Res Pract*. 2021;15(5):568. doi: 10.4162/nrp.2021.15.5.568
56. Mohd Ali M, Hashim N, Abd Aziz S, Lasekan O. Pineapple [*Ananas comosus*]: a comprehensive review of nutritional values, volatile compounds, health benefits, and potential food products. *Food Res Int*. 2020;137:109675. doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2020.109675
57. Varilla C, Marccone M, Paiva L, Baptista J. Bromelain, a group of pineapple proteolytic complex enzymes [*Ananas comosus*] and their possible therapeutic and clinical effects. A summary. *Foods*. 2021;10(10):2249. doi: 10.3390/foods10102249
58. El-Shazly SA, Ahmed MM, AL-Harbi MS, Alkafafy ME, El-Sawy HB, Amer SAM. Physiological and molecular study on the anti-obesity effects of pineapple [*Ananas comosus*] juice in male Wistar rat. *Food Sci Biotechnol*. 2018;27(5):1429–38. doi: 10.1007/s10068-018-0378-1
59. Kargutkar S, Brijesh S. Anti-inflammatory evaluation and characterization of leaf extract of *Ananas comosus*. *Inflammopharmacol*. 2018;26(2):469–77. doi: 10.1007/s10787-017-0379-3
60. Arruda HS, Borsoi FT, Andrade AC, Pastore GM, Marostica Junior MR. Scientific advances in the last decade on the recovery, characterization, and functionality of bioactive compounds from the Araticum fruit [*Annona crassiflora* Mart.]. *Plants*. 2023;12(7):1536. doi: 10.3390/plants12071536
61. Ramos LPA, Justino AB, Tavernelli N, Saraiva AL, Franco RR, De Souza AV, et al. Antioxidant compounds from *Annona crassiflora* fruit peel reduce lipid levels and oxidative damage and maintain the glutathione defense in hepatic tissue of Triton WR-1339-induced hyperlipidemic mice. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2021;142:112049. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2021.112049
62. Justino AB, Pereira MN, Peixoto LG, Vilela DD, Caixeta DC, de Souza AV, et al. Hepatoprotective properties of a polyphenols-enriched fraction from *Annona crassiflora* Mart. fruit peel against diabetes-induced oxidative and nitrosative stress. *J Agric Food Chem*. 2017;62(2):4428–38. doi: 10.1021/acs.jafc.7b01355

63. Justino AB, Franco RR, Silva HCG, Saraiva AL, Sousa RMF, Espindola FS. B procyanidins of *Annona crassiflora* fruit peel inhibited glycation, lipid peroxidation and protein-bound carbonyls, with protective effects on glycated catalase. *Sci Rep.* 2019;9(1):19183. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-55779-3
64. Salehi B, López MD, Martínez-López S, Victoriano M, Sharifi-Rad J, Martorell M, et al. Stevia rebaudiana Bertoni bioactive effects: from in vivo to clinical trials towards future therapeutic approaches. *Phytother Res.* 2019;33(11):2904–17. doi: 10.1002/ptr.6478
65. Orellana-Paucar AM. Steviol glycosides from Stevia rebaudiana: an updated overview of their sweetening activity, pharmacological properties, and safety aspects. *Molecules.* 2023;28(3):1258. doi: 10.3390/molecules28031258
66. Stamataki NS, Crooks B, Ahmed A, McLaughlin JT. Effects of the daily consumption of stevia on glucose homeostasis, body weight, and energy intake: a randomised open-label 12-week trial in healthy adults. *Nutrients.* 2020;12(10):3049. doi: 10.3390/nu12103049
67. Papaefthimiou M, Kontou PI, Bagos PG, Braliou GG. Antioxidant activity of leaf extracts from stevia rebaudiana bertoni exerts attenuating effect on diseased experimental rats: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nutrients.* 2023;15(15):3325. doi: 10.3390/nu15153325
68. Mathur S, Bulchandani N, Parihar S, Shekhawat GS. Critical review on steviol glycosides: pharmacological, toxicological and therapeutic aspects of high potency zero caloric sweetener. *Int J Pharmacol.* 2017;13:916–28. doi: 10.3923/ijp.2017.916.928
69. Nikolova K, Velikova M, Gentscheva G, Gerasimova A, Slavov P, Harbaliev N, et al. Chemical compositions, pharmacological properties and medicinal effects of genus *Passiflora L.*: a review. *Plants.* 2024;13(2):228. doi: 10.3390/plants13020228
70. Ożarowski M, Karpiński TM. Extracts and flavonoids of *Passiflora* species as promising anti-inflammatory and antioxidant substances. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2021;27(22):2582–604. doi: 10.2174/1381612826666200526150113
71. Cabral B, Bortolin RH, Gonçalves TAF, Maciel PMP, De Arruda AV, De Carvalho TG, et al. Hypoglycemic and vasorelaxant effect of *Passiflora edulis* fruit peel by-product. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr.* 2021;76(4):466–71. doi: 10.1007/s11130-021-00921-8
72. Guan Y, Sun H, Chen H, Li P, Shan Y, Li X. Physicochemical characterization and the hypoglycemia effects of polysaccharide isolated from *Passiflora edulis* Sims peel. *Food Funct.* 2021;12(9):4221–30. doi: 10.1039/D0FO02965C
73. Dos Santos FAR, Xavier JA, Da Silva FC, Merlin JPJ, Goulart MOF, Rupasinghe HPV. Antidiabetic, antiglycation, and antioxidant activities of ethanolic seed extract of *Passiflora edulis* and piceatannol in vitro. *Molecules.* 2022;27(13):4064. doi: 10.3390/molecules27134064
74. Urrego N, Sepúlveda P, Aragón M, Ramos FA, Costa GM, Ospina LF, et al. Flavonoids and saponins from *Passiflora edulis f. edulis* leaves [purple passion fruit] and its potential anti-inflammatory activity. *J Pharm Pharmacol.* 2021;73(11):1530–8. doi: 10.1093/jpp/rgab117
75. Ferreira MRA, Lima LB, Santos ECF, Machado JCB, Silva WAV, Paiva PMG, et al. *Eugenia uniflora*: a promising natural alternative against multidrug-resistant bacteria. *Braz J Biol.* 2023;83:e274084. doi: 10.1590/1519-6984.274084
76. Falcão TR, De Araújo AA, Soares LAL, De Moraes Ramos RT, Bezerra ICF, Ferreira MRA, et al. Crude extract and fractions from *Eugenia uniflora* Linn leaves showed anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial activities. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2018;18(1):84. doi: 10.1186/s12906-018-2144-6
77. Oliveira PS, Chaves VC, Bona NP, Soares MSP, Cardoso JDS, Vasconcelos FA, et al. *Eugenia uniflora* fruit [red type] standardized extract: a potential pharmacological tool to diet-induced metabolic syndrome damage management. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2017;92:935–41. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2017.05.131
78. Bello EF, Ezeteonu AI, Vincent U. In vitro therapeutic potential of leaf extract of *Eugenia uniflora* Linn on acute inflammation rat model. *J Dis Med Plants.* 2020;6(2):31–8. doi: 10.11648/j.jdmp.20200602.11
79. Sobeh M, Hamza MS, Ashour ML, Elkhatieb M, El Raey MA, Abdel-Naim AB, et al. A polyphenol-rich fraction from *Eugenia uniflora* exhibits antioxidant and hepatoprotective activities in vivo. *Pharmaceuticals.* 2020;13(5):84. doi: 10.3390/ph13050084
80. José MFB, Machado RP, Araujo PAB, Speretta GF. Physiological effects of yerba maté (*Ilex paraguariensis*): a systematic review. *Nutr Rev.* 2023;81(9):1163–79. doi: 10.1093/nutrit/nuac109
81. Masson W, Barbagelata L, Lobo M, Nogueira JP, Corral P, Lavalle-Cobo A. Effect of yerba mate (*Ilex paraguariensis*) on lipid levels: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Plant Foods Hum Nutr.* 2022;77(3):353–66. doi: 10.1007/s11130-022-00991-2
82. Santos D, Frota EG, Vargas BK, Tonieto Gris CC, Santos LFD, Bertolin TE. What is the role of phenolic compounds of yerba mate (*Ilex paraguariensis*) in gut microbiota? *Phytochemistry.* 2022;203:113341. doi: 10.1016/j.phytochem.2022.113341
83. Soares RA, Mendonça S, de Castro LÍ, Menezes AC, Arêas JA. Major peptides from amaranth (*Amaranthus cruentus*) protein inhibit HMG-CoA reductase activity. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2015;16(2):4150–60. doi: 10.3390/ijms16024150
84. Sferrazzo G, Palmeri R, Vanella L, Parafati L, Ronsisvalle S, Biondi A, et al. *Mangifera indica L.* leaf extract induces adiponectin and regulates adipogenesis. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2019;20(13):3211. doi: 10.3390/ijms20133211
85. Buchwald-Werner S, Schön C, Frank S, Reule C. Effects of *mangifera indica* (Careless) on microcirculation and glucose metabolism in healthy volunteers. *Planta Med.* 2017;83(10):824–9. doi: 10.1055/s-0043-103017

86. Pett KD, Alex PG, Weisfuss C, Sandhu A, Burton-Freeman B, Edirisinghe I. Mango consumption is associated with increased insulin sensitivity in participants with overweight/obesity and chronic low-grade inflammation. *Nutrients*. 2025;17(3):490. doi: 10.3390/nu17030490
87. Heena D, Trivedi S. Carica papaya: Potential implications in human health. *Curr Tradit Med*. 2019;5(4):321–36. doi: 10.2174/2215083805666190705170022
88. Singh SP, Kumar S, Mathan SV, Tomar MS, Singh RK, Verma PK, et al. Therapeutic application of Carica papaya leaf extract in the management of human diseases. *Daru*. 2020;28(2):735–44. doi: 10.1007/s40199-020-00348-7
89. Satankar V, Pandiselvam R, Sayed AAS, Senapathy M, Anitha T, Singh S, et al. Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) seed: a low-volume, high-value byproduct for human health and the food industry. *Food Chem*. 2022;386:132694. doi: 10.1016/j.foodchem.2022.132694
90. Kumar M, Tomar M, Amarowicz R, Saurabh V, Nair MS, Maheshwari C, et al. Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) leaves: nutritional composition, phytochemical profile, and health-promoting bioactivities. *Foods*. 2021;10(4):752. doi: 10.3390/foods10040752
91. Kumari S, Rakavi R, Mangaraj M. Effect of guava in blood glucose and lipid profile in healthy human subjects: a randomized controlled study. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2016;10(9):BC04–7. doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2016/21291.8425
92. Braga DCA, Gomes PM, Batista MAC, de Souza JA, Bastos JCSA, Rodrigues-das-Dôres RG, et al. Effects of *Psidium guajava* L. leaves extract on blood pressure control and IL-10 production in salt-dependent hypertensive rats. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2022;155:113796. doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2022.113796
93. Debnath B, Singh WS, Manna K. A phytopharmacological review on *Ananas comosus*. *Adv Tradit Med*. 2023;23:291–8. doi: 10.1007/s13596-021-00563-w
94. Justino AB, Pereira MN, Vilela DD, Peixoto LG, Martins MM, Teixeira RR, et al. Peel of araticum fruit (*Annona crassiflora* Mart.) as a source of antioxidant compounds with α -amylase, α -glucosidase and glycation inhibitory activities. *Bioorg Chem*. 2016;69:167–82. doi: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2016.11.001
95. Corrêa de Souza LA, Parreiras Costa G, Fracasso JAR, da Costa LTS, Barbosa DB, Zoppé NA, et al. Phytochemical profile, cytotoxicity, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antiglycation activity of *annona crassiflora* extract: an in vitro study. *Cosmetics*. 2025;12:36. doi: 10.3390/cosmetics12020036
96. Carvalho NCC, Monteiro OS, da Rocha CQ, Longato GB, Smith RE, da Silva JKR, et al. Phytochemical analysis of the fruit pulp extracts from *Annona crassiflora* Mart. and evaluation of their antioxidant and antiproliferative activities. *Foods*. 2022;11(14):2079. doi: 10.3390/foods11142079
97. Rojas E, Bermúdez V, Motlaghzadeh Y, Mathew J, Fidilio E, Faria J, et al. Stevia rebaudiana bertonii and its effects in human disease: emphasizing its role in inflammation, atherosclerosis and metabolic syndrome. *Curr Nutr Rep*. 2018;7:160–70. doi: 10.1007/s13668-018-0228-z
98. Carrera-Lanestosa A, Moguel-Ordóñez Y, Segura-Campos M. Stevia rebaudiana bertonii: a natural alternative for treating diseases associated with metabolic syndrome. *J Med Food*. 2017;20(10):933–43. doi: 10.1089/jmf.2016.0171
99. Panelli MF, Pierine DT, de Souza SLB, Ferron AJT, Garcia JL, Santos KCD, et al. Bark of *passiflora edulis* treatment stimulates antioxidant capacity, and reduces dyslipidemia and body fat in db/db mice. *Antioxidants*. 2018;7(9):120. doi: 10.3390/antiox7090120
100. Salles BCC, da Silva MA, Taniguthi L, Ferreira JN, da Rocha CQ, Vilegas W, et al. *Passiflora edulis* leaf extract: evidence of antidiabetic and antiplatelet effects in rats. *Biol Pharm Bull*. 2020;43(1):169–74. doi: 10.1248/bpb.b18-0095z
101. Peixoto Araujo NM, Arruda HS, de Paulo Farias D, Molina G, Pereira GA, Pastore GM. Plants from the genus *Eugenia* as promising therapeutic agents for the management of diabetes mellitus: a review. *Food Res Int*. 2021;142:110182. doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2021.110182
102. Mutha RE, Tatiya AU, Surana SJ. Flavonoids as natural phenolic compounds and their role in therapeutics: an overview. *Futur J Pharm Sci*. 2021;7(1):25. doi: 10.1186/s43094-020-00161-8
103. Pereira-Netto AB. Tropical fruits as natural, exceptionally rich, sources of bioactive compounds. *Int J Fruit Sci*. 2018;18(3):231–42. doi: 10.1080/15538362.2018.1444532
104. Reyes-García V, Benyei P, Aceituno-Mata L, Gras A, Molina M, Tardío J, et al. Documenting and protecting traditional knowledge in the era of open science: insights from two Spanish initiatives. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2021;278:114295. doi: 10.1016/j.jep.2021.114295
105. Wan MLY, Co VA, El-Nezami H. Dietary polyphenol impact on gut health and microbiota. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*. 2021;61(4):690–711. doi: 10.1080/10408398.2020.1744512
106. Mohan R, Jose S, Mulakkal J, Karpinsky-Semper D, Swick AG, Krishnakumar IM. Water-soluble polyphenol-rich clove extract lowers pre- and post-prandial blood glucose levels in healthy and prediabetic volunteers: an open label pilot study. *BMC Complement Altern Med*. 2019;19(1):99. doi: 10.1186/s12906-019-2507-7
107. Baraniak J, Kania-Dobrowolska M. The dual nature of amaranth-functional food and potential medicine. *Foods*. 2022;11(4):618. doi: 10.3390/foods11040618
108. Sirvent P, Chavanelle V, Otero YF, Bargetto M, Le Joubiou F, Boisseau N, et al. TOTUM-63, a plant-based polyphenol-rich extract, improves glycaemic control in subjects with prediabetes or early stage newly-diagnosed type 2 diabetes in a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2022;24(12):2331–40. doi: 10.1111/dom.14817